

PALAEOPORTOLOGY

Ancient Coastal settlements, Ports and Harbours

Volume V:
Bibliography

1st edition (2026)

Compiled by Arthur de Graauw

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Couverture :

Amarna Letter EA 153 of king of Tyr Abimilki to pharaoh Akhenaton (ca. 1360-1332 BCE):

"[...] The entire land is afraid of the troops of the king, my lord. I have manned my ships in view of (the coming) of the troops of the king, my lord. Whoever has disobeyed has no family, has nothing alive. [...]"

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1 INTRODUCTION

This project was started in 2010, aiming at collecting, identifying and locating ancient ports and harbours. It led to an extensive Catalogue including thousands of places. Much attention was also devoted from the onset to structural aspects as described by Vitruvius, and as resulting from modern coastal engineering such as design waves and harbour silting-up. Additional attention was devoted to ancient ships and sailing, as they define the harbour needs.

This work is reported in **5 volumes**, all available in **pdf versions**, and most of it is reproduced on the web site:

Volume I: Catalogue of Ancient Ports gives a list of ancient coastal settlements, ports and harbours with latitudes/longitudes, based on the works of ancient and modern authors.

Volume II: Citations of Ancient Authors gives citations of known ancient authors explicitly mentioning ports and harbours, in French. This work is not available on the web site as it would take too much space.

Volume III: Ancient Port Structures presents:

- Some thoughts on the design of several ancient ports (Actium, Alexandria, Apollonia, the Bosphorus, Caesarea Maritima, Carthage, Centumcellae, Delos, El Hanieh, Leptis Magna, Marius' canal, Narbonne, the Nile Delta, Nirou Khani, Portus, Pisa, Puteoli, Sharm Yanbu-Charmothas, Thapsus, the Tigris-Euphrates Delta, Tyre);
- A list of nearly **150** proposed locations for potential ancient harbours;
- Some comments on ancient port structures, like Vitruvius' methods, failure of breakwaters, subsidence and breakwater remains, design waves, reinforced concrete, pilae and arched breakwaters, pierced stones, defensive harbour chains, harbour silting-up, tombolos and salients;
- Some notes on ancient merchant ships and galleys, sailing techniques and Mediterranean sailing routes;
- Some thoughts about ancient trade networks and intermodal hubs;
- Some remarks on ancient maps, on ancient measures and ancient climate, including earthquakes and tsunamis.

Volume IV: Stories of Ancient Sailors provides around twenty stories of ancient sailors ... just for the pleasure of reading, in French.

Volume V: Bibliography provides thousands of references on ancient ports and harbours.

The present tenth edition of this work (**xxxxxxx xxth, 2026**) comes after a ninth edition (February 6th, 2024), an eighth edition (February 8th, 2022), a seventh edition (March 5th, 2020), a sixth edition (June 21st, 2017), a fifth edition (March 8th, 2016), a fourth edition (January 1st, 2014), a third edition (February 26th, 2013), a second edition (March 29th, 2012) and a first edition (September 19th, 2011).

Grenoble, **xxxxxxx xxth, 2026**

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This bibliography was set up with the Zotero software which can host thousands of references and return them in any of the numerous available “styles” (we chose the popular “APA”, 7th edition style). This bibliography contains nearly 4000 references which were accumulated during my 15-years research on ancient ports. The references are grouped into a number of sections and presented in alphabetical order of authors. The sections are related to a number of subjects (Sea Level Rise, Roman concrete, Ships and sailing, etc.) and to 18 geographical areas. A few references therefore appear in several sections, e.g., in the section “Sea Level Rise” which takes references from the geographical sections.

Except a few books to be bought in a library, nearly all documents listed below are freely available as pdfs on internet.

Despite its size, it makes no claim to be complete, merely listing the documents I have used in my studies of ancient ports.

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